

SAILING IN ADOLESCENCE: A CASE STUDY OF SEXUAL HEALTH EDUCATION AND EFFICACY AMONG GRADE 11 STEM AT THE GOOD SAMARITAN COLLEGES, INC.

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to deepen the understanding of sex education and its efficacy by exploring the viewpoints of Grade 11 STEM students, utilizing a case study as the research design, and assessing their knowledge about sexual health education to examine how it influences their awareness and behaviors regarding sexual activity, teenage pregnancy, and sexually transmitted diseases. This study consisted of fifteen (15) Grade 11 STEM students from Good Samaritan Colleges Inc. for the academic year 2024–2025. The researchers used a qualitative research method and used convenience sampling to select participants based on their accessibility and availability. Data was collected through primary sources, specifically using a structured open-ended questionnaire and interviews administered through Google Forms to the students across various Grade 11 STEM sections of The Good Samaritan Colleges, Inc. Results indicated that the sex education goes beyond just biological information, encompassing emotional and relational aspects too, highlighting the importance of a safe, open, and supportive environment that respects individual privacy and acknowledges personal boundaries. The study highlighted the beneficial role of sex education in fostering informed and responsible decision-making, increasing awareness of potential consequences, and promoting mutual respect and healthy relationships.

Keywords: *Sex Education, Case Study, Adolescence, Awareness, Interview*

INTRODUCTION

The risk of teenage pregnancy and sexually transmitted illnesses (STIs), including HIV, is increased when credible information is lacking; As a result, there has been very little attention to younger adolescents' voice and agency in relation to civic participation and opportunities for decision-making (Wickramanayake, 2019). Leading to more problems that our society faces today, HIV infections are rapidly rising in the Philippines, where the incidence increased by 543% between 2010 and 2023, according to Santos (2024). Meanwhile, in 2022, 5.4% of women between the ages of 15 and 19 reported having a previous pregnancy, and 1.6% reported being pregnant at the time, according to PSA (2023). These ongoing issues caught the attention of different experts and organization around the globe, putting the blame on poor sex education, online dating and conservative attitude cause by the country being deeply religious, in the increasing cases of the HIV (Sodipe & Presse, 2024).

In response to the increasing number of teenage pregnancies and STDs in the country, the Department of Education (DepEd) has released policy guidelines for implementing Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE), emphasizing a curriculum that upholds learners' rights to health education, information, and care. This DepEd order establishes standards for the efficient and effective teaching of CSE (Demographic Research and Development Foundation, Inc., 2018). Thus, some municipalities have enacted ordinances to prevent teen pregnancy and have set up adolescent-friendly centers that offer youth access to information, counseling, medical consultations, and risk assessments, according to De Castro-Villa (2021), yet the cases of STDs and teenage pregnancy still increase.

There's a need to emphasize better sex education in homes and schools, along with more accessible health services for adolescents, to address a 35 percent rise in pregnancies among girls aged 15 and under in the Philippines between 2021 and 2022 (Save the Children, 2024). Numerous misconceptions about sex education cause the public to view it negatively, often wrongly believing it encourages kids to engage in sexual activity at an earlier age and take more risks, even though this claim is scientifically unfounded (Myths about Sex-Ed, 2023). Bernardo stated that you're not encouraging youth to have sex but rather enabling them to make responsible decisions (MBT Desk, 2023). On the other hand, a study conducted in Nigeria reveals that sex education helps adolescents develop responsible attitudes and behaviors toward sex, promoting a healthier sexual life. Most participants demonstrated a strong understanding of sex education, and over half showed a positive attitude toward it, indicating a significant connection between knowledge and attitude regarding sex education (Ademuyiwa et al., 2022).

Sex education equips individuals with reliable information about reproductive health, contraception, and sexually transmitted infections (STIs); it has also been linked to lower rates of teen pregnancies and prevention of sexually transmitted infections (Sawade, 2024). Providing accurate information about the risks of unprotected sex and the serious dangers it can pose and teaching about contraceptives that can prevent STDs, according to Panchal (2023).

This study entitled *Sailing in Adolescence: A Case Study of Sexual Health Education and Efficacy Among Grade 11-STEM at The Good Samaritan Colleges, Inc.*, aims to expand the existing knowledge toward sex education and its efficacy by understanding the perspectives of Senior High School 11 STEM students at The Good Samaritan Colleges, Inc., and provide a locale study that other future research may use to expand a topic relevant to this study.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the perspective and experiences of Senior High School Grade 11 STEM Students toward Sexual Health Education and its Efficacy at Good Samaritan Colleges Inc.

Specifically aims to answer the following problems:

1. What is the Socio Demographic of the participants in terms of:
 - 1.1 Sex
 - 1.2 Age?
2. What is the existing knowledge of participants about Sexual Health Education and its efficacy?
3. How the participants perceive Sexual Health Education in terms of:
 - 3.1 Sexual Activity
 - 3.2 Teenage Pregnancy
 - 3.3 Sexual Transmitted Diseases?
4. What are the Positive and Negative takes of participants in terms of Sexual Health Educations and its Efficacy?
5. How participants apply their existing knowledge to raise their sexual awareness?

METHODOLOGY

This study focused on the perspective of the participants towards sexual health education and its efficacy. The different demographic profiles that may describe the participants were their sex and age. Meanwhile, in the areas of sexual health education and its efficacy, participants' perceptions were limited to the knowledge they possess in terms of sexual activity, teenage pregnancy, and STDs. The participants of this study include a total of fifteen (15) Grade 11-STEM students from The Good Samaritan Colleges Inc., Academic Year 2024–2025. The participants were selected based on convenience, considering what was most accessible for both the participant and the researchers. Moreover, this study used qualitative methodology, utilizing an explanatory case study design. Case study research requires in-depth investigation conducted into an individual, group, or event to gain an understanding of a real-life phenomenon. It is often used in the social sciences and humanities to explore complex issues and to provide insights into specific phenomena or situations (Coombs, 2022).

The researchers used a research-made instrument based on the research objective, employed with a structured questionnaire for the study, which was divided into

five sections: participants' socio-demographic information, existing knowledge about sex education, perceptions of sex education, views on its positive and negative aspects, and the role of sex education in promoting sexual awareness, whereas each section comprised two to three items of question. The structured interview was distributed to the participants through Google Forms.

RESULTS

Table 1. Age of the Participants

Age	Frequency	Percentage
16	10	66.67%
17	4	26.67%
18	1	6.66%
Total	15	100%

Table 2. Sex of the Participants

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	5	33.33%
Female	10	66.67%
Total	15	100%

Result showed that participants described Sex Education with diverse and wide-ranging interpretations. Out of fifteen (15) participants, eleven (11) of them mentioned sex education by its vital role in society, that covers a broad range of topics such as anatomy, reproduction, and sexuality. Furthermore, participants emphasized the importance of sex education in helping individuals make responsible and informed decisions, particularly regarding sexual activity, teenage pregnancies, and sexually transmitted disease. They also linked Sex Education to respect, consent, emotional awareness, and mutual understanding. Additionally, one (1) participant also highlighted the need for sex education to be accessible across different settings, such as in schools, homes, and online platforms. Overall, the responses showed that sex education serves to promote personal well-being and social responsibility.

However, the result of research objectives two: existing knowledge about sex education showed nine (9) out of fifteen (15) participants expressed feeling comfortable discussing their sexual activity. They attributed this comfort to factors such as open-mindedness, the normalization of the topic, and the respectful approach to sex education within the given context. However, six (6) of the participants did not share the same level of comfort, particularly when the discussion became too personal or depending on the setting (e.g., in a classroom). The participants' discomfort commonly caused by the feelings of embarrassment, concerns about privacy, and cultural norms.

Moreover, the result of research objectives three: perceptions of the participants about sex education showed that the majority of the participants strongly support sex education stating that it positively impacted individuals' way of thinking, highlighting its beneficial role in enhancing individual decision-making by providing the knowledge needed to make informed and responsible choices. This, in turn, leads to a reduction in sexually transmitted diseases and teenage pregnancies, contributing positively to society overall. Additionally, six (6) of the participants also noted that sex education encourages respect and supports healthy relationships, fostering responsible and empathetic behavior toward oneself and others. However, one (1) participant acknowledged that inadequate or incomplete sex education could result in confusion, misinformation, and unintended curiosity if not communicated effectively. Additionally, the eight (8) respondents emphasized the vital role sex education plays in empowering individuals, especially adolescents to make responsible choices about their sexual health and relationships.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 represented the age of the participants. The result showed that the majority of the participants' age was 16, with a frequency of 10, or 66.67%, while the age of 17 was 26.67%, with a frequency of 4, and the age of 18 was 6.67%, with a frequency of 1. It indicated that the population being studied was primarily composed of younger individuals. This result is supported by the study of Vasilenko (2018), "The National Longitudinal Study of Adolescent to Adult Health" is uniquely suited to understanding sexual development across adolescence into adulthood.

Table 2 represented the sex of the participants. The result showed that the majority of the participants' sex was female, with a frequency of 10, or 66.67%, while the sex of male was 33.33%, with a frequency of 5. It indicated that females had more participants available and willing to participate. This result is supported by the study of Rao & Nagaraj (2015) that "Each stage is associated with unique physiological changes. Females are commonly affected by various disorders in relation to this sexual response cycle."

However, the responses showed that sex education serves to promote personal well-being and social responsibility. It equipped young individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary for making informed, respectful, and responsible decisions. It is supported by Aguilar et al. (2024) that comprehensive sexuality education (CSE) covers the biological, emotional, and relational aspects of sexuality, guiding children and

adolescents in understanding its cognitive, physical, emotional, and social dimensions. Its goal is to equip them with the knowledge and skills needed to build respectful relationships, support their overall health and well-being, and uphold their human rights. Furthermore, the finding implied that sex education extends beyond biological facts, addressing emotional and relational dimensions as well.

Additionally, the participants' discomfort is commonly caused by the feelings of embarrassment, concerns about privacy, and cultural norms in terms of how the participants perceive sexual health education. Thus, the finding indicated that while most participants are open to engaging in sex education discussions when approached respectfully, in appropriate settings, and within an educational context, some may still feel uncomfortable, particularly when the topic is introduced out of context. Suwarni et al. (2024) also emphasize the importance of fostering a secure, respectful, and inclusive atmosphere in sex education. It is supported by Donkor & Lariba (2017) that sex education plays a crucial role in reducing teenage pregnancy by providing young people with accurate information about sexual health, decreasing curiosity and susceptibility. It helps dispel myths, resist peer pressure, and encourage responsible decision-making, ultimately working to prevent unplanned pregnancies among adolescents. Similarly to this, Nyinabo (2024) states that comprehensive sexuality education (CSE) provides young people with vital knowledge and skills to make informed choices regarding their sexual health. It plays a key role in preventing STDs, including HIV/AIDS, by encouraging safe behaviors and improving access to youth-friendly health services. Moreover, the responses reflect a strong and shared belief that sex education is essential for promoting sexual health awareness and preventing STDs. It provides individuals with the necessary tools to make informed decisions and adopt practices that support safer sexual behavior. According to Mattingly (2023), comprehensive sex education supports individuals by promoting informed decisions, decreasing the likelihood of teen pregnancies and STIs. On the other hand, abstinence-only education often leads to misinformation and stigma, which can harm public understanding of sexuality and contribute to higher teen pregnancy rates, particularly in conservative communities. In accordance with this, Khatimah et al., (2025) stated that, sexual health education significantly impacts decision-making by equipping adolescents with essential knowledge, skills, and motivation to adopt safer sexual practices. It implied that participants demonstrated a clear understanding of sexual health education and its significant role in decision-making, agreeing that access to accurate, respectful, and well-structured information leads to more informed and responsible choices.

Lastly, sex education was associated not only with gaining self-respect and respect for others but also with learning about personal boundaries and developing open-mindedness and broader awareness. It was seen as more than just an academic subject; it was viewed as a practical life skill that helps individuals navigate real-life situations involving sexuality and relationships. In accordance with this, Yao (2023) stated that sex education enhances adolescents' self-awareness by teaching them about sexual physiology, psychology, and moral values. This education helps them gain a deeper understanding of their bodies, emotions, and relationships, which is essential for their healthy development. Moreover, it implied that sex education promotes self-awareness, responsible behavior, and informed decision-making. It plays a vital role in empowering

individuals to protect themselves, communicate effectively, and build healthy, respectful relationships. Additionally, the findings revealed the essential role of sexual health education in empowering individuals to make thoughtful and responsible choices. Participants overwhelmingly supported its importance, noting its positive effect on raising awareness about the risks and consequences associated with sexual activity.

Conclusions

Based on the data gathered, the following findings were summarized: The participants describe sex education as playing a crucial role in society, covering various topics including anatomy, reproduction, and sexuality. The participants highlighted its significance in helping individuals make informed and responsible choices, especially concerning sexual activity, teenage pregnancies, and sexually transmitted infections. Participants also associated sex education with the values of respect, consent, emotional awareness, and mutual understanding. Moreover, participants highlighted the role of sex education in empowering individuals by fostering informed and responsible decision-making. The result emphasized its critical role in promoting sexual awareness and preventing adverse outcomes like teenage pregnancy and STDs, portraying it as a tool kit that instill core values such as consent, respect, and the development of healthy, respectful relationships with partners.

Findings showed that most participants was feeling comfortable discussing sexual activity attributing this ease to factors such as open-mindedness, the normalization of the topic, and a respectful approach to sex education in environment. However, few participants expressed discomfort, often due to feelings of embarrassments, concerns about privacy and the influence of cultural norms. Additionally, there was strong support among participants for the belief that sex education can significantly lower teenage pregnancy rates. The participants explained that sex education raises awareness of possible consequences, encourages responsible choices, promotes the use of contraception and protection, and helps eliminate shame or misinformation surrounding sexual health factors that collectively contribute to the prevention of teenage pregnancy but few participants felt that its effectiveness may depend on how sex education is delivered and perceived. Participants also viewed sex education as means of empowerment, particularly in decision-making, by providing accurate and practical information. This perspective reflects the understanding of sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) and the importance of safe sexual practices of the participants. Also, result emphasized that sex education helps reduce risky behaviors by increasing awareness and knowledge, which not only lowers the incidence of STDs but also positively influences individuals' behavioral choices.

Participants expressed strong support for sex education, emphasizing its positive impact on individual decision-making by equipping people with the knowledge necessary to make informed and responsible choices. This, in turn, contributes to decrease in sexually transmitted infections and teenage pregnancies, benefiting society. Additionally, sex education was seen to promote respect and foster healthy relationships. However, a

few participants show a concern, stating that poorly delivered or incomplete sex education could lead to confusion, misinformation, and unintended curiosity.

Recommendations

Based on the initial findings and conclusions, the researchers recommend educational institutions to utilize the insights and results to develop more student-centered approaches that improve students' understanding of sexual health education and its efficacy. Since the perspective of 11 STEM students regarding sex education and its effectiveness has been examined; further research could investigate the factors that shape their attitudes toward sex education. Also, similar study with an expanded sample size may be undertaken to verify the consistency of these findings.

Due to limited time and resources, researchers face struggle with time management, especially since qualitative data is rich and complex, making its analysis both time consuming and demanding in terms of resources. Moreover, although qualitative analysis offers rich and detailed insights, the small sample size limits the researcher's ability to produce highly credible and dependable results. As a result, the findings may not be entirely applicable to the broader population, since individuals beyond the study group might possess differing perspectives and experiences.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers hereby declare that the research work presented in this manual is our original work, conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines and regulations of the GSC. We have not engaged in any form of plagiarism or academic misconduct, and all sources used in this research have been properly cited and acknowledged.

The researchers further declare that any use of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies in the research process has been transparently disclosed and utilized responsibly and ethically. AI tools were employed solely to support specific tasks and did not contribute to the generation of original research ideas, hypotheses, or conclusions.

The researchers understand the importance of maintaining data privacy and security and have taken all necessary precautions to safeguard patient information and uphold confidentiality throughout the research process,

The researchers acknowledge that they are solely responsible for the content and outcomes of this research. The researchers have critically evaluated all information and outputs generated by any AI tools used and ensured their accuracy and relevance.

The researchers

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